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Effect of media composition on growth and flower attributes of lisianthus [*Eustoma grandiflorum* (Raf.) Shinner]

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ABSTRACT

An experiment was conducted to study the effect of different media composition on growth and floral characters of lisianthus. The plants grown on media M₃ (2 coir peat : 2 sand : 1 soil) recorded the maximum number of branches per plant, more number of leaves per stem at flower opening, maximum leaf area and highest fresh root weight. The plants in same media flowered earlier than other media compositions and recorded the earlier harvest. In case of floral attributes, the media M₃ recorded the highest stem length and diameter, maximum cut flower weight and maximum flower diameter. The media M₂ (1 coir peat : 2 sand : 1 soil) recorded the maximum flower length. Thus, it was found that media M₃ containing 2 parts of coir peat, 2 parts of sand and 1 part of soil was best for cut flower cultivation of lisianthus.

Key words : Growth and floral attributes, lisianthus, media composition

INTRODUCTION

Lisianthus, also known as Texas Blue Bell or Prairie Gentian belongs to the family Gentianaceae. Generally, it produces bluish purple flowers but occasionally pink or white flowered plants are found in native stand (Frett *et al.*, 1988). It is one of the important cut flowers in world trade, which is gaining momentum in recent past and comes within top 15 cut flowers in international trade. Lisianthus does not need any foliage cover of other (filler) material to prepare a bouquet, due to its attractive, large sized, abundant foliage. Lisianthus is commercially propagated by seeds. As with most new crops, due to limited cultural information, commercial producers have struggled with different aspects of production and management of this crop. Presently medium consisting of peat and perlite is used. As this medium is costly, it increases the cost of production. Thus, utilisation of indigenous materials for media preparation is having great scope. An

experiment was conducted to study the effect of media composition using indigenous materials on growth and floral attributes of lisianthus.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted at Bangalore during December 1999 to May 2000. Paleted seeds obtained from USA were used for study. Coir peat, sand and soil (v/v) were mixed in different proportions, by varying the levels of coir peat (0.5, 1 and 2) and sand and soil at 2 : 1 ratio. Uniform plants with four leaves were transplanted to the pots. Plants were staked with single bamboo stick. Three replications were laid down and observations were recorded by selecting five plants at random from each replication. Statistical analysis and interpretation of data were done by following the Fisher's analysis of variance techniques as given by Panse and Sukhatme (1967). The results were compared at 5% level of significance.

Table 1. Effect of media composition on some important growth characters and flowering in *lisianthus*

Treatment	Number of branches/plant	Number of leaves/stem at flower opening	Leaf area (cm ² /plant)	Fresh root weights (g)	Days taken for flower bud appearance	Days taken for first flower opening	Days taken for 50% flowering	Days taken for harvest
M ₁ (0.5 coir peat : 2 sand : 1 Soil)	2.69	19.80	254.81	4.41	43.18	63.00	65.78	67.18
M ₂ (0.5 coir peat : 2 sand : 1 Soil)	4.53	33.60	1248.66	9.99	39.53	58.50	57.33	62.51
M ₃ (0.5 coir peat : 2 sand : 1 Soil)	5.56	34.22	1434.05	10.69	38.50	57.92	56.33	61.31
S. Em ±	0.084	0.410	12.846	0.462	0.113	0.327	0.458	0.415
C. D. (P=0.05)	0.254	1.229	38.162	1.385	0.339	0.980	1.372	1.242

Table 2. Effect of media composition on some important floral components of *lisianthus*

Treatment	Stem length (cm)	Stem diameter (cm)	Cut flower weight (g)	No. of buds/ stem	Flower size	
					Length (cm)	Diameter (cm)
M ₁ (0.5 coir peat : 2 sand : 1 soil)	44.32	0.29	22.47	13.11	6.48	7.63
M ₂ (0.5 coir peat : 2 sand : 1 soil)	59.00	0.50	53.31	19.80	6.71	7.90
M ₃ (0.5 coir peat : 2 sand : 1 soil)	63.49	0.54	60.23	22.11	6.41	7.91
S. Em±	0.307	0.006	0.393	0.274	0.064	—
C. D. (P=0.05)	0.922	0.018	1.178	0.822	0.191	NS

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data on different growth and floral attributes are presented in Tables 1 and 2. Media M₃ produced greater number of branches (5.50) which is significantly superior over other two media combinations. This may be due to the higher organic carbon of 1.2% and higher ED of 0.39 mmhos/cm. This result is in accordance with the results obtained by Meerow (1994) in ixora plants grown in coir based media. Highest number of leaves (34.22) was recorded in plants grown in M₃ and the higher N and other nutrients in these media helped in greater vegetative growth resulting in higher number of growth. Significantly higher leaf size (44.60 cm²) was recorded in plant grown in media M₃. This may be due to higher N content in the media M₃. The increased leaf size may also be due to higher water holding capacity of media M₃ due to the presence of higher proportion of coir peat. These results are in agreement with the findings of Boodley *et al.* (1983) in chrysanthemum. The plants grown on M₃ media produced greater leaf size per plant (1434.05 cm²). The plants growing in media M₃ recorded highest weight of roots (10.89 g). The findings are in agreement with the findings of Meerow (1994) in ixora. Significantly lower number of days for bud initiation (38.50 days after transplanting) was taken by plants grown in media M₃. This may be due to higher leaf number and leaf size resulting in increased photosynthesis which might have been responsible for early initiation of flower buds. These results are similar to the results obtained by Vita-M-De and De-Vita-M (1993) in lisianthus. The crop raised in media M₃ flowered earlier (57.92 days) than the other media. Number of days taken for 50% flowering was significantly lesser in media M₃ (56.33 days after transplanting). Significantly lesser number of days for harvest was recorded in plants grown in M₃ (61.31 days for transplanting).

The media combination of 2 coir peat :

2 sand : 1 soil recorded higher stem length of 63.49 cm. This may be due to the higher growth of plant due to higher nutrient status in the media, greater leaf size and leaf number and also greater root growth. Similar results were obtained by Karlovich and Fontend (1986) in chrysanthemum. Gisierod (1988) recorded taller plants when grown on coarse sphagnum peat moss. Organic matter increased the plant height in china aster (Scoltanzad *et al.*, 1982). Significantly higher weight of cut flower (60.23 g) was recorded in the M₃ media. Media had a significant effect on the diameter of stem. Media M₃ developed significantly higher stem diameter of 0.54 cm. Similar results were recorded by Hicklenton (1983). Significantly higher number of buds per stem (22.11) was recorded in media M₃. Similar results were recorded by Harbaugh *et al.* (1998). Significantly longer flower length (6.71 cm) was recorded in plants grown on M₂ media containing 1 part coir peat : 2 parts sand : 1 part soil. The reduction of flower length in M₃ media can be related to greater number of buds. Non-significant differences were recorded in flower diameter due to media. However, higher flower diameter (7.90 cm) was recorded in M₃ media.

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